

Architecting Dynamic Privileges in Protected Systems Through Hardening Identity and Access Management

Bassam Farroha, Deborah Farroha

Department of Defense

Fort Meade, MD

farroha@ieee.org, deborah.l.farroha@ugov.gov

ABSTRACT

Information sharing is a fundamental enabler in facilitating better business and security practices, where exchange of information automated. The goal is to design smart systems that monitor and control authorized data to propagate through between security domains to authenticated and authorized users, while removing unauthorized blocks as required by policy. The Department of Defense (DoD) and Federal Agencies have established an information strategy for their respective communities that implement the national level information sharing strategy. The inclusion of a comprehensive Identity and Access Management (IDAM) capability is a fundamental building block to address these strategies. Given that business and mission environments will transition to the use of virtual environments if only to achieve IT efficiencies, this paper discusses additional advantages inherent in virtual environments. If the security posture of the overarching enterprise relies on a layered defense strategy, the IDAM capabilities provide what may be a last line of defense for controlling access to critical enterprise information and resources. The study addresses the architecture, development, and implementation of IDAM capabilities in the Enterprise, as well as the required modification to function in a Cloud Environment.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Enabling the sharing of information remains a national priority, whether to support military missions, Government day-to-day operations, critical infrastructure services or business planning and execution. The National Strategy for Information Sharing [1] sets forth a plan for unifying the Nation's efforts to share terrorism related information. Both the DoD Information Sharing Strategy and the IC Information Sharing Strategy complement the National Strategy. This is evidenced by the DoD shift to a Net-Centric warfighting paradigm and reliance on allied and coalition force military operations, dependence on intelligence to sustain our homeland security, increased dependence to sustain our critical national infrastructure services, economic dependence on eBusiness, and the infrastructures necessary to sustain each of these. These dynamics continue to drive our dependence on IT enterprise services in the cyber world.

However, along with this comes the potential for disruption or exploitation of cyber attackers [2]. The statistics for cyber attacks continue to become more worrisome every day, whether for geopolitical (e.g., espionage or military advantage), terrorist, competitive positioning, cybercrime or personal agendas. We face this in a world where our reliance on operations with global partners has become a way of life, whether to enable global business operations or coalition warfighting partners. This has led to the need to support communities of interest (COIs) whether in a small corporate intranet or a global military enterprise.

With the prevalence and sophistication of cyber threats, most every enterprise has to adopt a defense-in-depth strategy. One objective of these is typically to implement and maintain positive control of our information sources and the enterprise services, networks and systems that provide it. Over the past several years, DoD has assessed the technical feasibility and operational viability of advanced system access control mechanisms. Leveraging the results of a Privilege Management (PvM) Operational Pilot initiative, the DoD initiated the

Privilege Management Enterprise Solutions program to deploy commercially available web portal PvM solutions.

These solutions use sophisticated decision engine technology to determine if a user (identified by his CAC ID credential) with characteristics or attributes (e.g., nationality, security clearance and mission responsibilities) associated with that identity should be given access to specific information (characterized by labels referred to as metadata). These decision engines can also be set up to consider mission environmental data (e.g., INFOCON or DEFCON levels). Access decisions are based on rules in the form of digital access control policies, defining how these factors will be used to make access decisions that balance mission need and security posture given the operational situation at hand.

2.0 ARCHITECTING IDENTITY AND ACCESS MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONALITY

The Government has been working to establish an architecture for IDAM planning and implementation [3,4]. Figure 1 depicts the framework or architecture adopted by the Federal CIOs. The DoD also issued an engineering blueprint for their implementation of Policy Based Access Control (PBAC) planning [5]. This paper is aligned with these efforts. Being able to allocate and control access to enterprise system resources is critical to ensure that the highest priorities are supported, during normal operations or when services are degraded (e.g., during system malfunctions, network outages, or peak demands). Leveraging systems engineering processes to ensure this management framework is viable will be critical to its success. Controlling access and sharing enterprise information is another facet of Identity and Access Management (IDAM), in this case to limit access to information that may be sensitive or classified, where distribution is intended to be limited to individuals, organizations (e.g., departments) or other segments of the enterprise population. Boundary defenses are one means of controlling that access to only those who are authorized to access the enterprise. However additional controls are needed to prevent access by inadvertent user error, adversaries that

penetrate the enterprise external protection boundaries, and trusted insiders with malicious intent.

Figure 1 Federal CIO Council Identity, Credential, and Access Management Framework for Dynamic Attribute Management

2.1 Identity Definition: An entity (human user or Non-Person Entity, NPE) can be granted access to a requested service, resource or information object. As shown in Figure 2, managing access has four underlying functions: identifying the requester (and recipient if different) and the characteristics or privileges that have been allocated to him; characterizing the information or resources being requested; making a decision whether the access request should or should not be granted; and enforcing that decision. The actual mechanisms for implementing these functions can range from a basic go/no-go structure to a more fine-grained control approach. Early solutions adopted a user name and password scheme to identify the requester, having an access control list of authorized users to make access decisions, and choosing to allow or prevent the requested access based on that decision.

Figure 2 System Identity and Access Management Functionality

2.2 Identifying and Characterizing the Requester (Identity Management): Within the context of an enterprise, a requester could be a human user, or a device, application, business process etc., which is referred to as a Non-Person Entity (NPE). Recently, the White House released a National Strategy for Cyberspace Identities [6]. There are a number of Identity Management strategies aligned with specific technologies (e.g., biometrics) or organizations, including the Department of Defense [7]. The identity of the requester is a fundamental consideration when making an access decision and may adopt the following:

- This can be as simple as a user having physical access to the enterprise, by virtue of being allowed entry to a

physically controlled facility by a user carrying and displaying a photo identification badge and the authentication provided by the visual inspection of the badge by a guard at an access control point. This approach can also be used to provide logical access to an enterprise, and to information and resources offered by the enterprise, such as requiring access to a physically protected workstation or terminal to obtain the logical access.

- Logical identity can be established by issuing a User Name and Password to each entity, where the user name is issued to identify the user, and the password provides a means to verify that the entity asserting the identity is authenticated as being on a list of authorized user name/password pairings.
- The availability of public key cryptography has given rise to the issuance of PKI certificates as identity credentials. Here, each entity is assigned a globally unique digital identifier, which is embedded in an identity credential that includes that identifier, some certificate management parameters (e.g., certificate identifier expiration date), and a public key that can be used by a relying party to authenticate the user, all bound by a digital signature of an authorized source.
- Use of biometrics for humans that can be validated against an authoritative source for the biometric data that is captured prior to or during a session.

Depending on the degree of sophistication of the enterprise access structure, it may be necessary to establish authoritative characteristics or attributes for the requester, typically bound to the identity. These characteristics may be established by various means, including:

- Implicit attributes associated with an identity mechanism such as every entity that has a photo identification badge for an organization holds an active Secret level security clearance.
- Attributes can be embedded within an identity token such as is the case within the DoD, where the PKI identity credentials provided in an entity's Common Access Card (CAC) contain with it an authoritative, basic set of attributes for that entity.
- Attributes can be contained in an authoritative database, e.g., one that is known to contain security clearances for entities in an organization. There are typically processes and procedures in place to ensure that the content of that database is accurate and controlled only by authorized operators or administrators.
- Attributes can also be provided by an authoritative Attribute Management enterprise service that either contains, or has access to attribute sources that are considered accurate and authoritative.

2.3 Characterizing the Requested Assets (IA Metadata): Another facet of an effective access control structure is to determine the characteristics of the resource being requested. If the resource is an information object, this can be accomplished in several ways, including the following:

- Characterization of information being requested based on the source of the information e.g., a repository on the

enterprise that has been controlled and ensured to contain information within a logical grouping, such as a particular classification level of information, a specific mission or community of interest, or has limited distribution

- Use of a simple tagging structure, where each data element contains with it some description of the attributes of that element; and
- Use of metadata, which is associated with each element of information that is bound to each data element; the metadata tagging can be managed within or external to the data element with which it is associated.

IDAM is a systems engineering process that can also be applied to other enterprise resources, such as transport mechanisms. Here, access may be based on the entity’s attributes and the characterization of the resource. In the example of a transport service, access could be based on the quality of service the current transport mechanisms can support. In this case, access control could be used to enforce a prioritization scheme, which ensures that only high priority transactions are permitted when transmission capacity is limited.

2.4 Making an Access Decision: Underlying the IDAM operation is the ability to make access decisions based on access rules. These rules may be explicit, as an access policy in a digital format used by a sophisticated decision engine, or implicit, such that if conditions are met (e.g., user possesses an authentic identity token), access is granted. IDAM techniques are typically characterized by the basis for making an access decision, as highlighted in Table 1.

<i>Access Control List (ACL)</i>	Access based on a requester being identified on a list of entities that have been approved to gain access. An operator has to administer the list of requesters that are authorized to gain access
<i>Identity Based Access Control (IBAC)</i>	Access based on the ability of requesters being able to establish their identity, such as being in possession of an identity token, ala a DoD Common Access Card, CAC
<i>Role Based Access Control (RBAC)</i>	Access based on the privileges a requester is granted based on their role (e.g., a Systems Administrator being granted the ability to modify the configuration of a workstation)
<i>Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC)</i>	Access based on an a priori set of access rules that typically include requesters establish their identity, along with a set of attributes that have been assigned to or associated with the user’s identity in an authoritative source; possibly attributes for the information being requested, and attributes related to the state of the operational mission environment
<i>Policy Based Access Control (PBAC)</i>	Access is based on a set of access rules in a structure similar to ABAC, however in this case the access rules are provided as digital policies that are managed dynamically by an Enterprise Security Management service, typically external to the access control mechanism
<i>Risk Adaptive Access Control (RAdAC)</i>	An advanced concept, extending a PBAC structure to include an assessment of the risk to the enterprise, information and mission [Ref 8,9]

Table 1 Characterization of Typical System Access Control Techniques

2.5 Enforcing an Access Decision: The ability to actually control access is the foundation of any IDAM capability. Without this capability, or with the possibility of an adversary being able to circumvent or bypass the enforcement mechanism, unauthorized entities have open access. Enforcement mechanisms can be provided by the following:

- Physical means such as being given a combination of a physical key to a locking mechanism that protects a resource.

- Embedded enforcement of an access decision within a resource that provides access such as a repository or mission system e.g., PK enabling of a mission application.
- An appliance that provides the mechanism to either allow or deny access. This appliance can then block or otherwise prevent access requests from being provided to the resource being requested.

3.0 MANAGING AND GOVERNING ACCESS IN AN ENTERPRISE ENVIRONMENT

From an enterprise perspective, selection of types of access control mechanisms can be influenced by the following:

3.1 Stability of Access Decision Factors – When the basis for access decisions is relatively stable, use of mechanisms such as ACLs lends itself more readily. Administrative processes typically required to maintain these lists are time-intensive and not particularly well suited to situations where significant changes and updates are required frequently. On the other hand, use of a flexible Attribute Management enterprise service where attributes can be easily managed, may be more responsive and thus, more operationally effective.

3.2 Degree of Granularity – Typically, more simplistic structures such as ACLs or IBAC may be adequate when coarse access decisions are needed, such as the ability to gain access to an enterprise based on membership in an organization. On the other hand, implementing fine-grained controls may be more suitable for granting access to information, where many factors may have to be considered to implement formal release policies established for each information object requested. Here an ABAC or PBAC structure may be more suitable.

3.3 Need to Support Unanticipated Users – The approach for establishing a requesters’ identity may be driven by the need to support entities that were not necessarily expected to require such access. For example, in a military operation, there may be a need to expand the involvement of personnel from other agencies e.g., intelligence analysts who were not initially anticipated. If the identity approach selected uses DoD credentials, each analyst identified initially would be issued a DoD credential. In this scenario, each new analyst identified would need to be issued a DoD credential. This would mean that each new analyst has to physically visit a DoD Registration Authority. That operator has to validate that the user’s registration is approved, establish the user’s true identity, registered him in a DoD repository of authorized users, and create and issue the user a PKI certificate.

The requester identity approach selected may be very appropriate for large user populations where users can be identified well in advance of their need for access. However, even if the approval, registration and issuance process could be expedited, the time required to register new personnel may have an adverse impact on the mission operation. It may be more effective to select an identification scheme that can recognize and authenticate identity credentials issued by other US federal agencies. Access control mechanisms such as ABAC and PBAC lend themselves to more sophisticated access control rules that can include provisions for allowing more flexible identification schemes

3.4 *External Partners* – Typically an enterprise will have to support interactions with partners across multiple autonomous partner enterprises. The selection of an IDAM approach may have to support these interactions. If these external partners are to be issued credentials and associated attributes used for members of the target enterprise, there may not need to be any distinctions. If it is not feasible to issue and manage identities of external partners, additional IDAM provisions need to be considered.

Recognizing that these partners will likely retain responsibility for their sovereign capabilities, enterprise owners may adopt a federation approach, which will bring members of the federation under a common governance structure. Federation members would develop, select and ratify federated specifications and policies, enabling interoperability and providing an understanding of potential risk that may be created when each owner authorizes each external connection. This approach would enable interoperability and still allow the owners to retain autonomy for their specific implementations. The IDAM solutions have to accept federated identity credentials, which are issued by an external enterprise and comply with standards, policies and processes approved by a federated governance body. The enterprise can choose to either implement a capability to authenticate these credentials, or interface to the external enterprise to use its authentication services. There are similar choices for managing attributes, where the enterprise can integrate external partners attributes within its Attribute Management services or enables access to attributes in the external enterprise.

Another approach to enable interoperability with external partners is to treat requests from these entities as authorized members of logical groups based on some membership criteria. It may be practical to accept any requests coming to the enterprise via a carefully controlled gateway. The IDAM structure could assign credentials with associated attributes and in essence proxy these requests using these credentials.

4.0 DEPLOYMENT OF SYSTEM ACCESS CONTROLS

Being able to control access requires careful deployment planning, which can be aligned with the physical and logical structure of the enterprise, and tailored for specific assets that require that access protection. As shown in Figure 3, there are several points where deployment of access control structures can be considered. There is traditionally an access control structure associated with user log-on to a workstation; a second could be at the point workstations access the enterprise such as an Network Access Control (NAC); another is at the point where a user on a workstation requests access to a transport service to obtain connectivity to an enterprise service or mission system; and then to request an associated service, or access to a mission system or to specific information within a such a system.

As depicted in the figure, PvM access controls are also needed at external and internal enterprise (security) boundaries, applications (mission data repositories) and enterprise services, and network devices (e.g., access to workstations and updating of router tables). Providing effective access control at boundary access points and gateways is a line of defense that typically requires high demand rates and fairly limited access decision

factors. On the other hand, as PvM access controls are deployed closer to information and resource assets, demand rates are lower; however there are typically more decision factors that have to be considered for every access request. It is not a one-size-fits-all situation.

Figure 3 Notional Enterprise System Access Control Points
Selection of access control structures at these various points would depend on the anticipated sources of requests, projections of the request demand rates, and the sophistication of the access decision (typically associated with the degree of granularity discussed earlier). Another factor may be possible physical limitations of devices that may be considered for implementation of an access control point e.g., log-on capability implemented in a constrained physical package such as a PDA, cell phone, or smart phone.

One representative example of the overarching selection and deployment considerations is for log-on at a workstation, which would typically be infrequent, limited to a restricted set or group of users, and requires a coarse decision (e.g., accept or reject a log-on attempt). Log-on of a workstation (and the associated user) to the enterprise has similar characteristics, but may need to be augmented with complementary services such as *single sign-on*, where a user is required to execute a log-on sequence once per session; from that point on, the single sign-on service would perform subsequent log-on sequences automatically, transparent to the user.

Deploying access controls at an enterprise service level, a transport service would expect to have significantly higher demand rates, and the access control decisions could be somewhat more granular, particularly if it is implementing a priority allocation scheme. The nature of controls at a mission system access point can vary; the demand rates would be based on the functions of the system and the mission dependence on access to the information it provides; it may also require very fine-grained control for information, possibly factoring in an access policy for each category of information object, the ability to accommodate dynamic changes in those policies, the identity and attributes of the requester (and possibly the recipient if that is different than the requester), the characteristics of the information object requested, and mission or environmental factors.

5.0 OPERATING IN A VIRTUALIZED SYSTEM ENVIRONMENT

With the rapid advances in the Information Technology (IT) marketplace, enterprise environments are not static. It is imperative that IA solutions keep pace with these advances.

The current emphasis on virtual processing and cloud services are viewed as the next major step in the resulting evolution, and IDAM capabilities have to be planned to adjust or evolve to function effectively in that environment.

5.1 How IDAM Would Work in the Cloud: At a functional level, IDAM services will be needed to operate in these environments, much the same as they would in more traditional enterprise structures. There are special concerns for controlling access that virtual environments do raise including:

- *In the Enterprise*, IDAM solutions have to provide a reliable and operationally effective capability to identify requesters, make access decisions and enforce those decisions for enterprise services, capabilities, systems, and information. The discussions above discuss the capabilities required for this scenario.
- *Applied to Cloud*, this situation considers an environment where IDAM solutions are implemented outside the cloud, but serve crypto devices and mechanisms that are implemented within the cloud. This scenario is appropriate to the extent that IDAM capabilities can be structured as a logically separate enterprise services. This could be the case for gateways and external connections where there may be physically separate embodiments demand rates are modest, and latency may not be critical. It does require that when requests for access are encountered, the IDAM services have to be invoked.
- The approach is desirable since the IDAM enterprise service could be implemented, controlled and operated as a traditional enterprise solution, offering the same level of reliability and confidence (assurance) as otherwise traditional IA solutions. This deployment approach may be consistent with requester identification and access decision formulation. It could be more complicated if the enforcement mechanisms are also centralized, rather than maintained closer to the resources being controlled. If these functions are implemented within the cloud, a means is necessary to ensure that the enforcement mechanisms are invoked and cannot be bypassed.
- *In the Cloud*, there are considerations in addition to those discussed above. These are primarily concerned with the ability to identify and authenticate requester (and if different, recipient) identities, characterize the requested resource or information object (depending on the IDAM approach adopted), formulate an access decision and enforce that decision in a virtual environment. The scenarios discuss the overall functionality needed within a traditional enterprise and the implications of invoking an IDAM service and enforcing access decision performed in a cloud. The scenario extends to include considerations for implementing IDAM identity management and decision formulation processes in the cloud as well.
- Depending on the access control approach adopted, these functions may be tightly coupled to many other enterprise capabilities including: managing identity credentials and attributes; administering authorizations (e.g., ACLs if they are adopted); characterizing enterprise service resources typically using enterprise management capabilities; characterizing information objects (enterprise metadata

management; controlling access rules (if they are dynamically managed like a Policy Management service); obtaining mission attributes; and of course identifying which decision factors are needed, obtain those factors, and formulating an access decision. Access to authoritative providers of these factors is simplified if they are also implemented within the cloud environment. If they are addressed external to the cloud, the IDAM solutions have to consider the implications to maintaining access via the cloud's external interface protection.

- By addressing these functions within a cloud environment does reopen the possibility of deploying these capabilities closer to the information and resources being protected, which could address concerns about latency. However, it does raise considerations for reliability, assurance of invocation, protection against the possibility of bypassing or otherwise circumventing the IDAM capabilities, assurance that the correct factors are accessed and the decision formulation being performed correctly, of course the access decision is enforced properly.
- *Public versus Private Clouds* impacts the population that is allowed unrestricted access to the cloud environment. The embodiment for IDAM capabilities is basically the same for either cloud structure. A public cloud is generally open to all, enabling open access to adversaries as well as those who have legitimate reasons for its use. Private clouds have some degree of protection to ensure that only those personnel and processes that are properly authorized can access the cloud. There is still concern with possible cyber attacks by adversaries that can defeat the private cloud's access control mechanisms as well as exploitation by subverted insiders. It may be necessary to incorporate more stringent protection and higher confidence (assurance) on the IDAM embodiments for use in public clouds. However since the enterprise security posture is dependent on the ability to ensure that only authorized entities can obtain access to critical enterprise resources and information, it is likely that implementation of the most effective protections would still be warranted.

5.2 New Threats and Weaknesses: The rapid advances that industry continues to sustain in IT makes the enterprise environment more attractive to users, increasing processing capacities and transmission speeds, enhancing applications and service capabilities, easing operations by users, reducing costs and enabling more efficient operations. The broader acceptance of enterprise capabilities by virtually every military, government, industry and personal community makes it a more attractive target for cyber attacks. The scope, sophistication and effectiveness of attacks continue to expand at an ever-increasing rate and are expected to continue at this pace.

5.3 From Boundary to fine granular protection: Operating in a virtual environment brings with it new threats and weaknesses that have to be considered. With Cloud computing, our data could literally be stored on the same server as our competitors or adversaries. Rather than having direct or even indirect control over your data, it's pretty much at the mercy of your provider.

The decision of putting critical data on a server that we don't physically control changes the fundamental security paradigm. The best approach in protecting data in this environment is adopting a fine grained access control where each data element is tagged with security meta-data that identifies its sensitivity level, originators, and authorized recipients. The second part is developing a real-time automated policy interpretation and application to all access points where new policy, threat level, and laws of the land are interpreted into digital policy that governs all access points. The last part is the development of an automated secure configuration management system that interrogated the secure audit system and applies patches, and policy restrains to ensure that all the enterprise components are secure to a predictable levels. Until we have the security issues resolved, most companies will keep their hardware and software resources under their internal control. When companies outsource data center functions, the protection of the data becomes a joint effort where the customer should be given access to the audit and monitoring reports.

5.4 Insider threat versus external attacks: Whether launching attacks from outside the enterprise and penetrating its boundary protection, or subverting insiders to launch attacks from within, it is becoming necessary to layer defenses. Controlling access to critical enterprise resources (services and information) is a critical protection measure. With the recent push to the use of virtual processing environments with what has become cloud technologies, threats have to be re-examined to determine what new vulnerabilities will surface that can be exploited by our cyber adversaries.

Private clouds provide some level of control to restrict or limit access to the services they provide. Beyond that, virtual implementations of IDAM embodiments still lack the physical control of those implemented in a traditional environment.

6.0 ALTERNATIVES

Within a virtual environment, there are basic options for IDAM implementations. User workstation or client log-on, by its nature is embedded within the client device. If the processing is embedded within the device, the type of enterprise does not impact the IDAM structure. Based on the implementation, there are alternatives to be considered in implementing IDAM structures. In some instantiations (e.g., thin clients) the log-on processing is performed in the enterprise. In these cases, the transactions between the user and that processing (via the client or workstation) have to be protected. With that, it is still necessary to incorporate some means to ensure that the processing is not bypassed or circumvented so accurate access decisions and their enforcement are assured.

Beyond initial log-on, IDAM capabilities will most likely be implemented in one form or another within the environment. As with traditional enterprise environments, there is the basic IDAM functionality required to identify and characterize the requester, make a decision to grant or deny access, and to enforce that decision. There are options for the locations for their deployments at various access control points across the enterprise, driven by which resources and information require access protection, the architecture of the overall enterprise. At each access control point, there are also options for selection of the access control techniques that are driven by the degree of

granularity needed, the latency that can be tolerated to retain mission effectiveness, the level of access control protection required, and the level of protection and degree of assurance that can be obtained given state-of-the-practice for each solution.

7.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The DoD and IC have both established an information strategy for their respective communities that implement the national level information sharing strategy. An IDAM capability is a fundamental building block to address these strategies. Given that business and mission environments will transition to the use of virtual environments if only to achieve IT efficiencies, this paper discusses additional advantages inherent in virtual environments.

If the security posture of the overarching enterprise relies on layered defense architecture, the IDAM capabilities provide what may be a last line of defense for controlling access to critical enterprise information and resources. Implementing IDAM capabilities separate from but interfacing to the cloud allows dedicated operations of what in essence becomes an enterprise service. Moving this implementation within the cloud drives the need to establish effective new approaches to ensure the quality and confidence (assurance) of the embodiments.

In a virtual system environment, there are several dimensions to the IDAM solution that will be needed to replace the confidence (assurance) that is implicitly provided by locally controlled and operated implementations. This includes assurance that each IDAM mechanism is invoked (replacing installation as an in-line process); that it is implemented and executed correctly (replacing the design assurance and analysis), that it obtains authoritative information to make an accurate access decision, and implements a means to enforce that decision.

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